

RTV control in the field in 1984 dry season (DS). Wet seedbeds of highly susceptible TN1 and susceptible IR22 were covered with nylon mesh immediately after sowing to protect seedlings from GLH. Starting 1 d after transplanting (DT), 8 insecticide applications were made at weekly intervals. Disease incidence was recorded at 60 DT.

The same materials and methods were used in a 1985 wet season (WS) trial, but insecticide applications were reduced to five.

In the 1984 DS, RTV infection in plots treated with any of the pyrethroids was significantly lower than in the untreated control. Cypermethrin gave the lowest RTV incidence (see table).

RTV control by 4 synthetic pyrethroids on 2 susceptible rices at IRR, 1984-85.

Insecticide ^a	Formulation	RTV ^b (% infected hills) at 60 DT			
		1984 DS		1985 WS	
		IR22	TN1	IR22	TN1
Cypermethrin	5 EC	7.8 a	9.6 a	2.5 a	29.6 ab
Ethoproxyfen	20 EC	7.8 a	21.7 abc	2.6 a	22.9 a
Alphamethrin	10 EC	11.5 ab	21.3 abc	3.9 ab	39.4 ab
Deltamethrin	2.5 EC	14.4 ab	29.7 bc	3.3 ab	24.1 a
Control		30.3 c	81.9 d	5.3 b	43.4 b

^aInsecticide was applied at 1, 8, 15, 22, 29, 36, 43, and 50 DT in the 1984 DS and at 1, 20, 34, 49, and 63 DT in the 1985 WS. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

In the 1985 WS, RTV infection was significantly lower on IR22 treated with ethoproxyfen and cypermethrin and on TN1 treated with ethoproxyfen and deltamethrin.

The degree of control with the synthetic pyrethroids improved with more frequent applications early in crop growth. On susceptible varieties, control of RTV by insecticides was low. □

Chemical control of rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzivora*

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A 2-yr study (1982-83) investigated chemical control of GM on irrigated rice in southwestern Burkina Faso, where the pest is prevalent.

Carbofuran at 1.2 kg ai/ha and deltamethrin at 2.5 g ai/ha in a randomized block design with 5 treatments and 5 replications were evaluated. Plot size was 32 rows of 20 hills. Silvershoots at 45, 60, and 75 d after transplanting were counted on 4 rows/plot. Yield was estimated from 20 rows/plot.

Chemical control of rice GM^a. Burkina Faso, 1982-83.

Chemical applied at indicated time					Damage (% silvershoots) 75 DT	Yield (t/ha)
0 DT	15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT		
1982						
-	-	-	-	-	26 b	5.39 b
Carbofuran	-	-	Deltamethrin	-	23 ab	6.31 a
Carbofuran	-	-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	18 ab	7.31 a
-	Deltamethrin	-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	20 ab	6.40 a
Carbofuran	-	Carbofuran	-	Carbofuran	16 a	6.68 a
1983						
-	-	-	-	-	21 bc	4.91 b
Carbofuran	-	-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	16 ab	6.46 a
Carbofuran	-	-	Carbofuran	-	11 a	6.91 a
-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	Carbofuran	-	11 a	6.12 a
-	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	Deltamethrin	11 a	5.91 a

^aDT = days after transplanting. In a column and in a year, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Treatments that included at least one application of carbofuran were effective

(see table). Yields were 1-2 t/ha higher than without treatment. □

Pest Control and Management

WEEDS

Herbicides to control weeds in transplanted rice

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In southeastern Rajasthan, labor for

manual weeding is scarce and expensive. I evaluated herbicides in kharif seasons 1984-85.

Seven herbicides at 2 rates of application were compared with hand weeding 20 and 40 d after transplanting (DT) and an unweeded check. The

experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

Weed seed (*Echinochloa crus-galli*) was broadcast at 5 kg/ha immediately after transplanting. Herbicides were applied 6 DT.